

Tetranuclear Metal Complexes of Copper(II) with *m*-Bis(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene and *m*-Bis(1,3,5-trioxo-5-phenylpentyl)benzene and Corresponding Macrocyclic Schiff Base Complexes Formed with *o*-Phenylenediamine

A. K. JANA and B. SAHOO*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

Tetranuclear copper(II) complexes with the hexaketone ions of *m*-bis(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene (THB) and *m*-bis(1,3,5-trioxo-5-phenylpentyl)benzene (TPPB) have been isolated. Reaction of the metal complexes with *o*-phenylenediamine gives their respective tetranuclear macrocyclic complexes. The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of infrared and electronic spectra. Cryomagnetic studies show that the compounds possess negative *J* values and are antiferromagnetic.

β -POLYKETONES and their metal complexes have been an exciting area of research during the last two decades¹⁻⁴. Tri- and tetra-functional ketones, their anions and their Schiff bases have proved to provide essential conditions of geometry and potential abilities to coordinate towards one or two metal ions. Measurements of magnetic susceptibilities over a range of temperature have provided a powerful probe to find magnetic exchange and molecular structure for these chelates. Syntheses of naturally occurring organic compounds involving the polyketones *via* their metal complexes have been a fascinating area of research in recent years and metal ions are believed to play an important role in these stereospecific reactions.

Considerable effort has been made for the isolation of binuclear macrocyclic metal complexes involving Schiff bases of triketones with diamines. However, all attempts have been so far unsuccessful. The facile hydrolysis at the carbon-nitrogen bond and possibly the inadequate ring size appear to constitute important factors and preclude incorporation of two metal ions into the macrocyclic ring. In a recent communication we have reported⁵ a series of tetranuclear nickel(II) complexes with hexaketones, *m*-bis-(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene (*m*-THB) and *m*-bis(1,3,5-trioxo-5-phenylpentyl)benzene (TPPB).

In our continuing research in the area we report the tetranuclear copper(II) complexes of these hexaketones, their characterisation and spectral properties. Magnetochemical studies from ambient to 80 K reveal spin-spin interaction, and the exchange is antiferromagnetic. Reaction of the tetranuclear complexes with 1,2-diaminobenzene gives a large macrocyclic ligand, that houses four copper(II) ions. The dimeric interactions are manifested through cryomagnetic studies.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of B.D.H. or S.M. quality. *m*-Bis(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene and *m*-bis(1,3,5-trioxo-5-phenylpentyl)benzene were prepared as reported earlier⁵.

Bis-[m-bis-(1,3,5-trioxonatehexyl)benzene]tetra copper(II), $Cu_4(C_{18}H_{14}O_6)_2$: A solution of cupric chloride dihydrate (1.36 g, 0.004 mol) in methanol (60 ml) was added to *m*-bis-(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene (0.66 g, 0.002 mol) in methanol (80 ml) followed by addition of a solution containing sodium hydroxide (0.32 g) in a minimum volume of water. A light green compound was formed readily and was refluxed for 1 h. The light green compound was filtered, washed with methanol and then by ether and finally dried in vacuum (Found: Cu, 28.7; C, 47.0; H, 2.80. $Cu_4(C_{18}H_{14}O_6)_2$ calculated Cu, 28.07, C, 47.68; H, 3.09%).

The deep green bis[*m*-bis-(1,3,5-trioxonato-5-phenyl-5-pentyl)benzene copper(II)] was prepared in a similar manner (Found: Cu, 21.5; C, 57.20; H, 3.00. $Cu_4(C_{28}H_{18}O_6)_2$ calculated Cu, 22.01; C, 58.23; H, 3.11%).

Copper(II) complexes with the macrocyclic Schiff base ligand derived from the hexaketones and o-phenylenediamine, $Cu_4(C_{48}H_{36}O_8N_4).4H_2O$: A solution of cupric acetate monohydrate (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) in hot methanol was added to *m*-bis-(1,3,5-trioxohexyl)benzene (0.66 g, 0.002 mol) in hot methanol (80 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. A solution of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.22 g, 0.002 mol) in methanol was added to it dropwise with constant stirring and the reflux was continued for 2 h more. During the course of the reaction colour of the compound changed from light green to deep green and finally to deep brown. The

product was filtered and washed with methanol and finally with ether and dried in vacuum (Found : Cu, 23.20 ; N, 4.80. $\text{Cu}_4(\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4)\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calculated Cu, 22.63 ; N, 99%).

The similar dark green macrocyclic complexes with TBPP and *o*-phenylenediamine was prepared in a similar way (Found : Cu, 17.69 ; N, 3.92. $\text{Cu}_4(\text{C}_{68}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4)\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calculated Cu, 18.54 ; N, 4.08%).

Results and Discussion

The tetranuclear copper(II)-hexaketonato complexes are readily formed in microcrystalline form by the reaction of the metal acetate or chloride with the respective ligands in methanolic or aqueous alcoholic solution. The *o*-phenylenediamine Schiff base complexes are conveniently obtained by refluxing the tetranuclear hexaketonato metal complexes in ethanol medium with the base in molar ratio 1 : 2.

Infrared spectra :

Hexaketonato copper(II) complexes : The hexaketonates exhibit a broad and strong band near 3400 cm^{-1} in the region $3100\text{--}2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and two other medium intensity bands precisely located in the region $2650\text{--}2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which originate due to stretching vibrations of OH groups involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. In the copper(II) complexes the broad band in the region $3100\text{--}2600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears implying break-down of the enolic OH bonds. A new broad band of medium to strong intensity, the centre of which lies near 3400 cm^{-1} , occurs in the spectra of the complexes on account of coordinated water.

In the fingerprint region the first strong band in the ligand appears near 1675 cm^{-1} which is characteristics of C=O stretching vibrations. In the copper(II) complexes this band shifts to about 1600 cm^{-1} on account of coordination. Apart from this band there are a number of vibrational bands that discern with CH_2 deformation, ring breathing vibrations of phenyl group in (TBPP) and CH out of plane vibrations and are not discussed here^{6,7}.

The structures of the complexes can be postulated as shown in Fig. 1, that are consistent with the important features of ir spectra. The postulated structure shows, that each hexaketonate ion acts as a polychelating agent coordinating towards a quadruplet of metal ions. The centres are constituted of two dimeric units linked through the central phenyl rings.

Schiff base complexes : The copper(II) complexes have a broad band near 3400 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to OH stretching vibrations of associated water. The complexes do not exhibit any band in the region $3300\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which could be attributed to N-H stretching vibrations and indicate condensation of both the NH_2 groups of *o*-phenylenediamine with the metal ketonato complexes.

R=OH, or C₆H₅

Fig. 1

In the region $1600\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ the ir spectra show two bands near 1600 and 1550 cm^{-1} which from their intensity and sharpness can be assigned to C=O and C=N stretching vibrations, respectively. Vibrational bands in the region $1400\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ resemble the general features of the spectra of free ketones. These spectral data manifest a macrocyclic quadrinuclear ring structure for the metal complexes where the terminal copper(II) ions are four-coordinated and planar with chromophore CuN_2O_2 . Further evidences are obtained for their structures from electronic spectra and magnetic properties (Fig. 2).

R=OH, or C₆H₅ ; L=H₂O

Fig. 2

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 1. The spectra of all the complexes show broad asymmetric bands in the region $13000\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in some cases can be resolved into two components. The asymmetric bands characterise d-d transitions of copper(II) ions, ${}^2\text{E} \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_2$, and their split components under octahedral ligand fields with distortions or under planar arrangements with each copper ion coordinated to four donor atoms of ketonato ions and their macrocyclic Schiff bases. Electronic transitions beyond 20000 cm^{-1} are intense and are assigned to charge transfer transitions.

Magnetic properties :

The magnetic susceptibility data have been analysed in terms of Heisenberg-Dirac-Van Vleck spin-coupling Hamiltonian as adopted by Kambe. The data agree well with a dimeric model, and the inter dimer-dimer coupling has been considered to be zero. For a copper diad the energy levels for

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Sl. no.	Ligand constituents	Formula of complexes	Ligand	Field bands	Charge transfer bands
1.	<i>m</i> -THB	Cu ₄ (C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₈) ₂	13400	16000	25000 29400
2.	TPPB	Cu ₄ (C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₈) ₂	13000	15800	24100 33250
3.	<i>m</i> -THB + <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine	Cu ₄ (C ₄₀ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	15600	19000	29400
4.	TPPB + <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine	Cu ₄ (C ₆₀ H ₄₄ O ₈ N ₄) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	—	18000	29000

S_{1,2} = 1 and 0 are ½ J and 3/2 J, respectively where J is the exchange coupling constant. When the system is subjected to external magnetic field the energy levels are split further into (2S_{1,2} + 1) levels, i.e. the first order Zeeman term of M_sgβH is to be added to the energy where g is the Lande splitting factor and M_s takes the value S_{1,2} to -S_{1,2}. The molar susceptibility is given by Van Vleck's equation,

$$\chi_M = \frac{N}{H} \left[\sum_i \frac{\delta E_i}{\delta H} \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{kT}\right) / \sum_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{kT}\right) \right]$$

and for the fact gβH is small compared to kT in the range of temperature of interest, the susceptibility equation for copper diad is

$$\chi_M = \frac{Ng^2\beta^2}{3kT} \times \frac{6 \exp(J/kT)}{1 + 3 \exp(J/kT)}$$

The susceptibility of the compounds have been determined over the temperature range 300 to 80 K. The values given in Table 2 have been corrected for

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF COPPER(II)-HEXAKETONATES

<i>m</i> -THB			TPPB		
Temp. K	χ _M × 10 ⁻⁶ c.g.s., e.m.u.	μ _{eff} B.M.	Temp. K	χ _M × 10 ⁻⁶ c.g.s., e.m.u.	μ _{eff} B.M.
304	720	1.27	298	760	1.30
298	700	1.25	271	790	1.27
250	740	1.18	240	820	1.22
219	790	1.13	165	1023	1.14
201	830	1.11	142	1160	1.11
175	920	1.09	120	1280	1.09
148	1045	1.07	98	1540	1.08
113	1316	1.06	84	1790	1.07
80	1795	1.06			

diamagnetism and Pascal's constants for all atoms and groups and for the temperature independent paramagnetism, N_α. The effective moment, μ_{eff} is given at each temperature using the equation, μ_{eff} = 2.827 [χ_M - N_αT]^{1/2}. The value 60 × 10⁻⁶ cgs emu for copper(II) has been used for N_α.

The susceptibility data are found to agree well with the dimeric model (Tables 2 and 3) and indicate

Fig. 3. Plot of χ'_M vs temperature and μ_{eff} vs temperature for Cu₄(*m*-THB)₂.

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF COPPER(II)-MACROCYCLIC COMPLEXES

m-THB			TPPB		
Temp.	$\chi_A \times 10^{-6}$	μ_{eff}	Temp.	$\chi_A \times 10^{-6}$	μ_{eff}
K	c.g.s., e.m.u.	B.M.	K	c.g.s., e.m.u.	B.M.
305	503	1.10	300	690	1.20
290	513	1.08	248	748	1.17
272	512	1.04	205	830	1.13
242	535	1.01	169	950	1.10
210	578	0.96	138	1162	1.10
188	598	0.95	107	1540	1.12
149	745	0.93	88	1915	1.12
122	835	0.91			
89	1020	0.85			

that the dimer-dimer interactions through the bridging phenyl groups are weak. The values for J , the exchange coupling constant, and g , the Lande' splitting factor were calculated for each compound and are recorded in Table 2. The observed susceptibility data were compared with the predicted behaviour by curve fitting procedure (Fig. 3).

The magnetic moments of each compound are found to fall with decrease of temperature and the

J values are negative. These results show that the spins of adjacent copper atom couple antiferromagnetically. The magnetic exchange interaction between the copper(II) ions are believed to occur through bridging oxygen atoms and the π system of β -polyketones, which have finite overlaps with the d orbitals of copper(II) containing the magnetic electrons. The results satisfy the proposed structures.

References

1. T. T. HOWARTH, G. P. MURPHY and T. M. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 517.
2. G. P. MURPHY and T. M. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 8253.
3. P. J. WITTEK and T. M. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 6865.
4. T. YANO, T. USHIJIMA, M. SASAKI, H. KOBAYASHI and K. UENO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, **45**, 2452.
5. A. K. JANA, N. P. RATH, B. SAHOO and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 371.
6. M. L. MILES, T. M. HARRIS and G. R. HAUSER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3884.
7. F. SAGAR, H. KOBAYASHI and K. UENO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, **45**, 794 ; 1973, **46**, 484.